

**MULTIDISCIPLINARY PRECEPTORSHIP IN SPECIALIZED TRAINING IN HEALTH:
THE PERCEPTION OF RESIDENTS AND PRECEPTORS**

PRECEPTORÍA MULTIDISCIPLINAR EN FORMACIÓN ESPECIALIZADA EN SALUD: LA
PERCEPCIÓN DE LOS RESIDENTES Y PRECEPTORES

PRECEPTORIA MULTIDISCIPLINAR NA FORMAÇÃO ESPECIALIZADA EM SAÚDE: A
PERCEPÇÃO DE RESIDENTES E PRECEPTORES

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Abstract

In accordance with the guidelines of multiprofessional residencies in health, the preceptor has the function of directly supervising the activities of the residents, preferably from the same professional category as the resident and be present at the place of practice. The objective of this study was to analyze the perception of residents and preceptors about preceptorship in primary health care services of a teaching-care unit linked to a public university in the state of Pará. The study had a qualitative approach and was descriptive and exploratory. Focus groups and Bardin's content analysis technique were used for data collection and analysis, respectively. Eleven professionals participated in the study, including preceptors and residents of the professional categories of Nursing, Physical Therapy and Occupational Therapy. The analysis resulted in two final categories: the characterization of the preceptorship and difficulties, potentialities and contribution of this activity to the resident professional. The study concluded that the participants yearn for the redefinition of the preceptor's practice by the institution's management bodies, with a focus on continuing education and improvement of skills and competencies aimed at in-service teaching activities.

Keywords: Preceptorship; Primary health care; In-service training; Multiprofessional residency in health.

Resumen

De acuerdo con los lineamientos de las residencias multiprofesionales en salud, el preceptor tiene la función de supervisar directamente las actividades de los residentes, preferiblemente de la misma categoría profesional que el residente y estar presente en el lugar de práctica. El objetivo de este estudio fue analizar la percepción de los residentes y preceptores sobre la preceptoría en los servicios de atención primaria de salud de una unidad de enseñanza-asistencia vinculada a una universidad pública del estado de Pará. El estudio tuvo un enfoque cualitativo, de carácter descriptivo y exploratorio. Para la recolección y análisis de datos se utilizaron grupos focales y la técnica de análisis de contenido de Bardin, respectivamente. Participaron del estudio once profesionales, entre preceptores y residentes de las categorías profesionales de Enfermería, Fisioterapia y Terapia Ocupacional. El análisis resultó en dos categorías finales: la caracterización de la preceptoría y las

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dificultades, potencialidades y contribución de esta actividad a la profesional residente. El estudio concluyó que los participantes anhelan la redefinición de la práctica del preceptor por parte de los órganos de gestión de la institución, con un enfoque en la educación continua y el mejoramiento de habilidades y competencias orientadas a las actividades de enseñanza en servicio.

Palabras clave: Preceptoría; Atención primaria de salud; Formación en servicio; Residencia multiprofesional en salud.

Resumo

Em concordância com as diretrizes das residências multiprofissionais em saúde, o preceptor tem por função a supervisão direta das atividades dos residentes devendo ser preferencialmente da mesma categoria profissional do residente e estar presente no local de prática. Objetivou-se analisar a percepção de residentes e preceptores acerca da preceptoría nos serviços de atenção primária a saúde de uma unidade docente-assistencial ligado à uma universidade pública no Estado do Pará. O estudo teve abordagem qualitativa e foi do tipo descritivo e exploratório. Os grupos focais e a técnica de análise de conteúdo de Bardin foram utilizados para a coleta e análise dos dados respectivamente. Participaram do estudo, onze profissionais entre preceptores e residentes das categorias profissionais de Enfermagem, Fisioterapia e Terapia Ocupacional. A análise resultou em duas categorias finais: a caracterização da preceptoría e dificuldades, potencialidades e contribuição dessa atividade para o profissional residente. O estudo concluiu que os participantes anseiam pela redefinição da prática do preceptor pelos órgãos de gestão da instituição com foco na educação permanente e aprimoramento das habilidades e competências voltadas as atividades de ensino em serviço.

Palavras-chave: Preceptoría; Atenção primária à saúde; Capacitação em serviço; Residência multiprofissional em saúde.

Introduction

In accordance with the guidelines for multidisciplinary health residencies, the preceptor's role is to directly supervise the residents' activities and should preferably be in the same professional category as the resident and be present at the practice site (Brazil, 2012a).

From this perspective, the preceptor plays an essential role, as in addition to teaching clinical practice, they are responsible for integrating the concepts and values of school and work, acting as a liaison between the learner and the health service. The necessary requirements for the preceptor are theoretical, didactic, pedagogical, and political knowledge, as well as collaboration in the ethical development of professionals in training (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2021).

It is necessary to consider the plural dimension of preceptorship and understand it as an action that occurs in a historical context with a culture established by preceptors, users of health services, residents and managers, each with their own ways of thinking and establishing practice (Botti; Rego, 2024).

Health services in the context of primary health care (PHC) provide contextualized training through the variability of demands brought by users; a greater degree of social immersion; the establishment of a bond with the health team and the use of teaching methodologies that go beyond the traditional, based on the problematization of the experienced reality (Miolo; Petermann; Fedosse, 2022).

The importance of in-service teaching is highlighted, through preceptorship for the strengthening of professional categories that make up the multidisciplinary team in PHC (Queiroz; Dimestein; Dantas, 2023).

Some teaching strategies used by preceptors in PHC are: direct and systematic observation, case studies and guided readings regarding the demands evidenced in the population served (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2023).

It is essential to consider the relationship between the preceptor and the student, and it is necessary to welcome and value the theoretical knowledge and feelings brought by the student at the beginning of their practice (Zilbovicius *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, the preceptor needs to be prepared to act as a mediator of the resident's expectations and establish objective guidance, interacting with a view to transformations in the way health care is developed (Siqueira, *et al* 2022).

In addition to technical mastery to perform the service, the preceptor needs to have confidence to conduct the teaching practice of residents, making it necessary to invest in preceptorship training that is adjusted to the needs of the preceptors (Souza; Cordeiro, 2020).

With interministerial ordinance 1077 of 12.11.2009, which provides for residency in a professional area and multiprofessional residency in health, the role of the preceptor was resized to enable in-service learning.

The Unified Health System (SUS), as the organizer of the training of human resources in health in Brazil, includes preceptorship as it enables reflection among health teams and managers, as well as transformations in work processes based on horizontal cooperation actions, institutional support, tele-education and health training (Brasil, 2017).

It is even necessary that such actions are continually adjusted to the context of health services (Paula; Toassi, 2021).

With the advent of the Multiprofessional Residency Program in Family Health in 2012 in the state of Pará, several health services began to provide practice settings, including a major teaching-care unit affiliated with a public university offering several undergraduate

programs, such as medicine, nursing, physical therapy, and occupational therapy, with a focus on primary care and medium-complexity care. With the advent of the residency program, the facility also began to accommodate residents from these professional categories, expanding the role of preceptorships in this setting.

The residency provided the unit's preceptors with a leading role in all resident-focused teaching activities, as well as greater dedication to preceptorship activities. This reality raised many questions among these preceptors regarding the in-service teaching process.

Furthermore, there was little opportunity for these preceptors to express expectations, impressions, and suggestions regarding the preceptorship activity in the residency, which remains ongoing, given the interinstitutional cooperation agreement signed over a decade ago, which has generated concern about avoiding work disconnected from the educational institution and the search for improvements.

Thus, the study aimed to analyze the perception of preceptors and resident professionals in family health about the practice of preceptorship in a teaching health center in order to verify the challenges, the favorable points and the suggested solutions for the difficulties evidenced in this scenario, thus reinforcing the collaborative role of these professionals in the systematization of teaching practices in health services.

Method

The study had a qualitative approach of a descriptive and exploratory type and was carried out on the premises of a school center linked to a public university in the State of Pará.

Data collection took place from March to May 2018. Eleven professionals from the categories of Nursing, Physiotherapy and Occupational Therapy participated in the study, four of whom were preceptors working in the outpatient maternal and child health care service and seven were residents in their second year of multiprofessional residency in Family Health.

The data collection technique used was focus group interviews, a type of interview or conversation in small homogeneous groups to encourage spontaneous expression and interaction between participants (Minayo, 2014).

A single script was adopted for the participants (Table 1), which was based on the theoretical framework on preceptorship in the context of PHC.

Table 1: Script used in focus groups.

- What do you understand by “preceptorship”?
- How does the initial contact between preceptors and residents occur?
- What activities are used by the preceptor in supervising and evaluating residents?
- Name one factor that hinders and another that facilitates the role of preceptors in the practice setting.
- What is the importance of preceptor-resident interaction for professional training in the SUS for you?

Source: Own authorship

The content of the focus groups was fully recorded. Preceptors and residents were interviewed in separate groups by a previously selected professional. The researcher acted only as a rapporteur to avoid influencing the participants' responses (Turato, 2013).

Two meetings were held with the residents and one with the preceptors, lasting two hours and thirty minutes.

For data analysis, Bardin's content analysis was used, a set of techniques designed to make inferences about participants' statements through the objective and systematic identification of the implicit content of communications (Bardin, 2011).

Pre-analysis consisted of the full transcription of the recorded content, followed by skim reading, selection of documents to constitute the analysis corpus and preparation of the material, with clipping and numbering of the text messages.

The next stage consisted of exploring the material, with data coding carried out from the recording units.

Next, categorization occurred with the classification of information by similarities and differences, creating initial categories (themes), which were regrouped, creating intermediate categories and two final categories.

For a representative analysis of reality, the categorization followed the criteria of exclusivity, objectivity, fidelity and productivity, recommended by Bardin to obtain good categories.

The frequency of appearance of words and the emphasis in the participants' reports were considered to avoid fragmentation of the message and the loss of implicit content (Bardin, 2011).

Data processing, inference and interpretation phase, the information was compared with the objectives and theoretical framework studied, and finally converted into an interpretative synthesis.

In accordance with the principles of resolution 466/2012 (Brasil, 2012b), the study was approved by the ethics committee on 11/29/2017 under registration CAAE/7997491710000514.

Results

The preceptors participating in the study had been working in outpatient services for over ten years, working thirty hours per week. The residents were in their final year of the Multidisciplinary Residency Program in Family Health and shadowed these preceptors on their shifts for three months before moving to another practice setting. The following final categories were obtained:

- Performance of the preceptor in the practice scenario

This category refers to the way the preceptor acts in the practice scenario under study, encompassing the understanding of the term *preceptorship*; the communication process established between the preceptor and resident and the methodology used by the preceptor for teaching in practice, as evidenced in Table 2.

Table 2: Progression statement for final category I.

Initial Categories	Intermediate Categories	Final Category
Sharing knowledge and experiences in the practice setting. Practice guidance.	Perception of the term preceptorship	Preceptor's performance in the practice setting
Effective aspects of preceptor-resident communication. Communication failures.	Characteristics of preceptor-resident communication	
Welcoming ritual Supervised practice Formative assessment X summative assessment.	Procedures used in the practice of preceptorship	

Source: Own authorship

The results expressed the variation in meaning of the term preceptorship, sometimes as an activity in which cooperativism predominates, marked by the sharing of experiences and knowledge between preceptors and residents; sometimes as the idea that it is up to the preceptor to assume the role of guide of the teaching-learning process in the practical setting.

It was evident that terms such as: friendship, professional colleague, welcome and company highlight the relational dimension of the preceptorship experience.

According to the study, the main in-service teaching activities in this scenario are the presentation of the practice site, observation of care, case studies, and continuous assessment of the resident.

The data revealed that the majority of preceptors and half of the residents conceive of preceptorship as an inherent element of the field of professional practice, expressing that these professionals are not unfamiliar with having to perform this activity.

Regarding the aspect of communication, the results indicated two distinct situations: the first indicated the effectiveness of preceptor-resident communication in the work process with its importance in highlighting learning needs, and the second highlighted the existence of obstacles that prevent more effective communication, such as little time to discuss the practice.

- Challenges, contributions and suggestions for preceptorship in the context of the multiprofessional residence at the school center

In this category, it was possible to glimpse the weaknesses of the preceptorship activity in the practice scenario as well as the points of greatest success, as demonstrated in table 3:

Table 3: Progression statement for final category II.

Categories Iniciais	Categories Intermediárias	Categoria Final
Devaluation of the preceptor. High demand for the service. Distance between preceptors and COREMU. Acting and teaching at the same time. Technical mastery of the preceptor. Safe and ethical posture of the preceptor. Availability to teach in service..	Limiting and enhancing factors of preceptorship	Challenges, contributions and suggestions for preceptorship in the context of the multiprofessional residency at the School Center
Awaken interest and motivation for service and scientific production. Encouraging protagonism. Promotion of service learning.	Preceptorship contribution to resident training	

Source: Own authorship.

The problems most emphasized by participants referred to the technical and organizational dimensions of the preceptorship activity.

The need to offer more spaces for dialogue between the educational institution and preceptors was strongly emphasized by the participants. This constituted a limiting factor for preceptorship in the school center, represented here by little opportunity to socialize important information for the progress of in-service teaching activities.

Furthermore, the lack of definition of selection criteria and performance monitoring for preceptors was mentioned.

The intense flow of services at the school center was mentioned by participants as an element that also hindered in-service learning.

Another aspect mentioned refers to preceptorship as a practice without financial incentives.

As positive aspects, most participants mentioned preceptors willing to perform preceptorship activities, as well as being aware of enabling the resident to have a successful experience at the school center, despite the difficulties listed.

It also stood out the professional recognition of the resident at the school center in the perception of the participants.

The technical mastery of preceptors in the context of PHC was cited expressively, which, according to the participants, provided a redefinition of personal values and professional preparation to work from the perspective of prevention and health promotion.

The preceptor's professional attitude was mentioned as fundamental for the residents' motivation and growing involvement in the service, in addition to awakening interest in the production of scientific knowledge based on practice.

Preceptors reported satisfaction with the fact that residents were able to achieve the established learning objectives and how much they themselves learned while performing their preceptorship.

Participants were then asked to suggest improvement actions for the difficulties mentioned as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Participants' suggestions for promoting improvements in preceptorship in the practice setting.

- Create internal regulations for preceptorship activities
- Organize a collegiate body with the participation of residents, preceptors, tutors, service managers and coordinators
- Establish criteria for selecting preceptors
- Schedule scientific events involving preceptors in the teaching-learning process, aiming to share experiences with the academic community.
- Create a culture of *feedback* and training for preceptors.
- Reset the induction week for preceptors at the beginning of residents' practice.

Source: Own authorship

Discussion

It was found that the meaning of the words, *knowledge* and *experience*, used mainly by residents, denotes their expectation of having preceptors with preparation and clarity regarding the role they play in the in-service teaching process, allowing the resident to contribute to this process (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2022).

The preceptors' commitment to sharing experiences and offering pedagogical support to the resident was evidenced by the ideas of more investment in preceptorship and review of teaching practices in health services (Fedosse; Miolo, 2020).

Therefore, it is necessary to reflect on how to manage the work process in the practice scenario, which is sometimes influenced by the conception of production, generating mechanization of health practices. Therefore, care must be taken to ensure that in-service teaching spaces are ensured (Souza *et al.*, 2025).

The gap between teaching and service at the school center has already been mentioned in a previous study on preceptorship, but from the perspective of outpatient rehabilitation services.

This study highlighted that the existing disarticulation between teaching and assistance coordination was reinforced by the absence of legal instruments on the practice of preceptorship, which interfered with the involvement of preceptors in planning teaching practice for students (Dias, 2014).

This fact is considered to be recurrent in the preceptor's routine in some practice scenarios, resulting in an adaptation of in-service teaching activities to the available time and space conditions (Ferreira; Soares, 2021).

This reality is mentioned in other studies on preceptorship in primary care, in which improvisation in in-service teaching practices contributes to distancing from the recommended learning objectives (Lima *et al.*, 2020).

Other studies consider that the preceptor accumulates the role of technician and educator in service, which are marked by many demands and productivity, a problem that is not restricted to medical residency preceptorship, but also to preceptors in other professional categories (Modesto, 2020).

In the view of the study participants, preceptorship required rapport, indicating the need for an investment of affection in the teaching and learning relationship capable of deconstructing representations that teaching practice is serious, indifferent and cold, and is therefore deprived of affection, one of the elements that condition human existence (Freire, 1996).

The reports also express that there is a need to consider communication between preceptor and resident not only as a means of promoting information, but also as a way of sharing knowledge and practices aimed at the service-learning process (Pasini *et al.*, 2020).

Furthermore, it is worth highlighting emerging teaching with a focus on developing autonomy for study, favoring a teaching/learning process based on the exchange of experiences and knowledge of each professional involved (Moreira *et al.*, 2022).

Close dialogue between residency programs and preceptors should guide preceptorship training activities and aim to perform health teaching actions based on reflection on the teaching methods used, assessment methods, and information and communication technology resources adopted (Rodrigues; Witt, 2022).

In this sense, it is suggested that the pedagogical preparation for these preceptors may be based on Andragogy, or learning for adults, by emphasizing the need for learning; autonomy to learn; prior knowledge of the participant; interactivity; encouragement of reflection on the work process and *feedback* (Lawall *et al.*, 2023).

A viable suggestion would be to provide this group with training in learning areas that would include: presentation of the residency program's pedagogical project; preceptor competencies in residency in PHC settings; active teaching methodologies; and the importance of reflection on practice.

Conclusion

The study allowed us to understand the tensions and potentialities in the experience of teaching and learning in the context of multiprofessional residency in a primary health care service linked to a public university in the State of Pará.

Preceptors and residents listed some difficulties of preceptorship, most vehemently cited: the challenge of acting and teaching at the same time in a setting with high demand for services; reduced communication with the educational institution; and weaknesses in the preceptor preparation process.

It is important to highlight that it is also necessary to listen to the health service manager and users in order to verify the impact of teaching practices on the quality of care actions developed in this scenario.

The focus group methodology allowed participants to express their impressions, which highlighted the need to create spaces for discussion and sharing expectations to improve health teaching practices in this group.

Participants' desire for review of preceptor monitoring practices by responsible institutional management bodies is intense, which can be mitigated by investing in institutional actions focused on continuing education, pedagogical training, and greater participation of preceptors in the residency program coordination, including scientific initiation groups.

Finally, it is necessary to invest in creating a culture of continuous evaluation of preceptorship activities, considering the particularities of each preceptor's performance, establishing a path for the development of skills and abilities in this group that increasingly contribute to the training of new health professionals

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